

Wood-Cement Composites as Engineering Materials

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Abstract

Producing these plates started in Austria in 1914. The main purpose of production wood-cement panels is the combination of organic particles such as wood and lignocellulosic materials with minerals connectors such as Cement, Plaster and Magnesium and etc. Wood-cement composites have desired functional properties such as resistance against atmospheric and fire factors, Silencer properties, thermal insulation and biological factors and also have high dimensional stabilities. In addition to the production of flat panels, using appropriate molds the products such as cement blocks, bricks and shaped parts can be produced. One of the conventional Wood-cement products which is dated back more than half a century in the United States is Excelsior panels or Wood strand cement pages. These panels are being used in buildings especially in ceilings and walls interior coatings. The light and heavy products are being produced from Portland cement. In the light products straw and in the heavy products particles or fibers are being used. The products with the light density are being used as interior ceiling or partition. In addition, these products are being used as decorative applications. Heavy panels can be used for floors, ceilings, flameproof doors, load carrier walls and cement molds. The molding products with complex shapes can also be produced easily. Thus decorative ceiling tiles can also be produced. In this paper the effect of fibers or lignocellulosic materials on the cement composites has been studied. These cement composites have been reinforced with the wood particles. The advantages of these composites is environmental compatibility. They also can be used as an important element in the lightening of buildings due to the low density. They play a key role in the reducing of building weight. Consequently, they can be economical and also they can cause to reduce earthquake force absorption.

1. Preface

Wood composites which are linked with cement have potential to provide a large number of products for building applications by utilizing a wide range of recycled wood. Recycled magazines and newspapers, old pallets (old board), cutting wood wastes, agricultural wastes and tree small diameters stems can be used both for current products and laboratory products. The value of this products will improve when a better understanding of manufacturing process and matter properties was found. The development and the application of these composites is a confirmation of the amount of attention to them as engineering materials. In addition to fire resistance, these materials have a particular interest for using in hot weather and humidity where the heat and the corrosion are of great importance. These composites can be designed so that they provide a range of unique properties of energy since these properties will be useful for resisting against strong wind pressures and earthquakes. These features are of architects and contractors interests to use this materials in public buildings and multi-family apartments. More information about the strength, hardness and flexibility in wood-cement composites require to be developed the acceptance and using them in building applications. Recently, the industry has focused on developing products which are made of cement reinforced with fibers. These products contain 8 to 10 percent of wood chips weight and their appearance and durability are important instead of their strength and hardness. Material resources and current demands for recycling concluded that it is time for recognizing the problems and the related properties of these composites so that using them for building applications in residential areas is developed. According to the World Bank report the number of

residential units in Iran is 198 units per one thousand people. These statistics show that Iran is far behind in this part of the world standards. The useful life of buildings in our country is 25 to 35 years while in European countries the useful life of buildings is over 100 years. The major problems that has been led to this 70-year-old dramatic differences are non-standard materials, lack of proper calculations and designing in accordance with consultant standards, lack of supervisor engineers accurate monitoring in various stages of construction, lack of skilled and experienced personnel and qualified executives, lack of using modern technology.

The current design of buildings increases the use of heavy materials. Thus the dead load of building increases so that in such buildings the risk of earthquake is at high level. Some experts believe that in our country the dead load of each square meter of building is 400 to 500 kg over than common global standards and criteria.

2. The purpose of study

In this research, it is necessary to study the practicality of engineering product development and also it is necessary to extract the unique properties of Wood-cement composites. The purpose of this paper is to familiarize engineers with wood - cement composite which can be used as an engineering material in the building industry. These materials can cause to reduce the weight of structure. Consequently it can cause to reduce forces and becoming economic. For developing of engineering composites from the undervalued resources a set of fundamental measures should be taken.

3. Studies and investigation

Cement is one of the most widely used materials in the field of composite. Cement products which are reinforced by wood fibers were developed as an alternative to Asbestos cement. These materials were developed 25 to 30 years ago. In 1920 some studies in Europe using wood chips in cement became fashionable for making of building blocks. In 1940, there were a number of manufacturers companies which were producing a special wood-cement composite as Wood Wool and were using wood in it. Wood Wool was suitable for using sound absorption and fireproofing walls and ceiling panels. The interest in cement reinforced with wood fibers created a spark in the process of utilizing glass wool fabrics after World War II. So that some private companies considered cellulose fibers as replacement for glass in the cement reinforced with fibers. Since glass wool have many risks for human health it seems that using the cellulose fibers is essential. Over the past 25 years, American Association of Concrete has supported a research for developing cement composites reinforced with fibers with high performance. The primary task of fibers in these cement composites is increasing the break energy by bridging between the gaps. In fact the fibers prevent concentrating the tension at the crack tip. For this reason, they delay the brittle fracture and increase the flexibility of composite. Indeed, reinforcement is done by fibers for correcting break rigidity.

4. The stiffness and the flexural strength

The studies which has been conducted on flexural strength of the wood- cement composites are part of the overall efforts for developing high performance fiber-reinforced cement products. Mainly concrete in the structural work has a pushing resistance in the range of 20 to 35 MPa. Adding wood particles or cellulose fibers will improve rigidity through closing the direction of cracks disseminations. This causes the composite can tolerate the load. Energy absorption properties of wood-cement composites causes rigidity is considered as a valuable criterion so that the benefits of adding wood fiber or wood particles in the cement can be found. Soroushian showed that there is often a linear increase in the rigidity with the amount of fiber and by increasing the amount of humidity the rigidity will increase. Coutts also proved this relationship which has been shown in the figure 1. Soroushian et al. have reported that cement reinforced with wood fibers have a flexural strength of between 7 and 30 MPa which depends on the mass

of fibers, moisture and the type of fiber.

Figure 1 shows that how these parameters affect the flexural strength.

Figure 1. Flexural strength in terms of amount of fibers. The information shows the effect of the fibers, kind of fibers (Kraft mass in terms of thermo mechanical mass) and refining properties method (Autoclave method in terms of refining properties by the air).

Figure 1.

Coutts linked the loss of flexural strength to the fiber features. The moisture causes the fibers would seem more flexible and consequently the possibility of preventing the spread of cracks in some constructions would be reduced. Coutts showed that thermo mechanical pulps are not resistant as well as wood pulps. He attributed these results to the fibers damages during the pulp manufacturing process. These fibers damages are created due to the influence of them on the cement adsorption by the extraction of polysaccharides and fatty acids. On the other hand, these damages stay during the preparation process but they go out in the chemical pulping process. Coutts also studied the process of properties improvement in the autoclave. Autoclave composites contain a mixture of Portland cement and fine sand which are combined with wood fibers and are steamed for 8 hours at 170 to 180°C. This refining process will be caused that strength reduces after applying thermo mechanical pulp but when kraft pulp is used the maximum strength of 20 MPa will be achieved. Properties improvement through the air that takes 14 to 28 days will give the flexural strength 30 MPa to the composite. The composites are prepared with a mixture of 8% Kraft pulp. Wood - cement composites include a wide range of ingredients. They also include a wide range of flexural strength. Nassiri et al. in their studies used Bagasse fiber with the cement. Bagasse has been refined mechanically. In these studies Nassiri et al. use Calcium chloride in two levels of 4 and 10% as catalyst and three levels 5.7, 5, 10 percentages of cement weight. These percentages cause to neutralize the cement absorption limiting factors. But consuming of more than 5% based on dry weight of

cement has negative effect and causes to increase the rate of hydration. This process causes the tension in the compositions. Figure 2 shows that by increasing the amount of calcium chloride the flexural strength reduces gradually.

Figure 2.

In this composite standard DIN 68763 is used in order to making sample. To conduct this experiment INSTRON 1186 testing machine is used with the loading speed of 5 mm per minute. The sample size was $5.1 \times 5 \times 28 \text{ Cm}^3$. By reducing the fiber level from 10 to 4 percent the flexural strength will be increased and the reason of this issue is improving the hydration process. This issue causes stronger connection between fibers and cement. On the other hand, by shrinkage of the fibers during the drying process and by concentrating the tension some small cracks will be created at the interface between the fiber and cement. By increasing the amount of fibers these cracks will be increased and the flexural strength will be decreased (Table 1).

Fibers(%)	Flexural strength)MPa(
4	6/623
10	5/632

Table 1. The flexural strength values

Dousthosseini and Yazdi in their studies about the effect of 4 kinds of additives calcium chloride, water glass, aluminum sulfate and ferric sulfate on the functional properties of the concrete panels made of poplar wood have reported that the functional properties of the boards which are made of calcium chloride as a catalyst have a significant improvement compared to other boards. The reason of such issue can be attributed to the better hydration of the cement because of the calcium chloride and neutralizing a greater percentages of the limiting factors which prevent cement adsorption. On the other hand, by increasing the consumption from 3 to 5% the quality and functional properties of these panels will be improved which have the desirable physical and mechanical properties at the level of 5%. Bylba et al. in their studies about the effect of herbal blend of Bagasse fibers on the fiber-cement composites adsorption have reported that unlike raw Bagasse the treated Bagasse shows a better behavior and higher strength properties.

5. Conclusion

The preliminary studies show that these materials can be used to resist the effects of temperature and humidity but they require further research and development in order to evaluate shear strength, rigidity,

connections and creep under constant load. These materials should be developed so that we need the efforts to implement the instructions of the standard assessment for simplifying the recognition of the effect of additives and processing variables on the mechanical properties. Furthermore, it should be available some standard methods which identify and introduce properties report methods such as the amount of moisture, the amount of fibers, density, wood species, geometry, orientation and order placement. According to the results, there are many benefits to the combination of wood and cement so that using such composites in the building seems to be more effective. The preliminary studies show that some wood-cement composites have properties which are considered as civil engineering materials. According to the results, it seems that the most prominent features of these materials is rigidity. Matching of standards for building and evaluating the structural performance will help the scientists to conduct a study for accepting of these composites as engineering materials and also for developing them in order to use the recycled wood materials.

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